

CORRELATION BETWEEN CENTRAL FOVEAL THICKNESS AND HBA1C IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a prevalent metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia, which can lead to microvascular complications, including diabetic retinopathy (DR) and diabetic macular edema (DME). Central foveal thickness (CFT) measured by Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a key parameter for assessing macular health. This study aimed to explore the correlation between CFT and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in patients with Diabetes Mellitus.

Methods: An observational study was conducted over six months, including 200 patients with confirmed diabetes mellitus attending Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Data collected included demographic details, diabetes duration, HbA1c levels, and CFT measurements obtained via OCT. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software, with correlations evaluated through Pearson's correlation coefficient, and associations analyzed using the chi-square test.

Results: The study found a significant positive correlation between HbA1c levels and CFT ($r = 0.446$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that higher HbA1c levels are associated with increased retinal thickness. Conversely, a significant negative correlation was observed between diabetes duration and CFT ($r = -0.264$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that longer diabetes duration is associated with a thinner central fovea. The findings emphasize the critical role of glycemic control in influencing macular changes in diabetic patients.

Conclusion: Poor glycemic control, as reflected by higher HbA1c levels, is significantly associated with increased central foveal thickness, a key indicator of diabetic macular edema. Regular monitoring of CFT using OCT and maintaining HbA1c levels below 7% are essential strategies for preventing DME and reducing the risk of visual impairment in diabetic patients.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetic Macular Edema, Central Foveal Thickness, HbA1c, Optical Coherence Tomography.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia due to impaired insulin production, insulin action, or both. It poses a significant global health challenge, with millions of people affected worldwide (1). Persistent high blood sugar levels in diabetic patients can lead to various microvascular complications, one of the most prevalent being diabetic retinopathy (DR) (2).

Diabetic retinopathy is a progressive eye disease that affects the retinal vasculature, causing damage to the retina due to prolonged exposure to elevated blood glucose levels (3). Among the retinal structures, the macula, which is crucial for central vision and high visual acuity, is particularly vulnerable. In advanced stages of diabetic retinopathy, diabetic macular edema (DME) can develop, where fluid accumulates in the macula, leading to swelling and thickening of the central fovea, potentially causing vision impairment or loss (4).

The uvea, comprising the iris, ciliary body, and choroid, may also be impacted due to the inflammatory processes and vascular dysfunction associated with diabetes (5). These complications can further exacerbate macular changes, affecting the visual prognosis of diabetic patients.

Central foveal thickness (CFT), a critical parameter reflecting macular health, is commonly measured using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) (6). OCT is a non-invasive imaging technique that provides high-resolution cross-sectional images of the retina, enabling precise measurement of retinal thickness and detection of subtle changes in retinal architecture (7). By measuring CFT, OCT can help detect macular edema early, monitor disease progression, and evaluate the effectiveness of treatments in diabetic patients (8,9).

Understanding this relationship may provide insights into the impact of systemic glucose control on macular changes and help in the early identification of patients at higher risk for visual impairment, guiding more tailored management strategies. Hence this study was planned with the aim to explore the correlation between central foveal thickness and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in patients with Diabetes Mellitus

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This observational study was conducted over six months and included a sample size of 190 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. The study population comprised patients attending the Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion criteria, which encompassed individuals of any age or gender with a known history of diabetes mellitus. Exclusion criteria

included patients with significant cataract or other media opacities interfering with fundus evaluation, retinal pathologies such as retinal vascular occlusions and age-related macular degeneration, a history of photocoagulation, or prior intravitreal anti-VEGF injections.

Following approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee, the study adhered to ethical standards, ensuring informed consent, patient confidentiality, and data protection throughout. Comprehensive data were collected, including socio-demographic details, type of diabetes, duration, glycemic control, HbA1c levels, and clinical symptoms, recorded in a case proforma. A thorough ocular examination was performed, which included visual acuity assessment using Snellen's chart, anterior segment evaluation under a slit lamp, gonioscopy where necessary, intraocular pressure measurement via non-contact tonometry, and direct and indirect ophthalmoscopy for posterior segment evaluation. Central foveal thickness was measured using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), a non-invasive imaging technology useful for both qualitative and quantitative assessment of the macula.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software (IBM version 26.0). Continuous variables were tested for normality, and descriptive measures such as mean, standard deviation, and range were calculated for normally distributed data. Differences between groups were assessed using the Student's t-independent test, while the association between HbA1c levels and diabetic macular edema status was evaluated using the chi-square test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant

RESULTS

The study included 200 participants with a mean age of 55.02 years (SD = 8.386), ranging from 39 to 73 years. The duration of diabetes among participants ranged from 1 to 25 years, with a mean duration of 9.58 years (SD = 6.208). Regarding gender, 65% were male (n = 130) and 35% were female (n = 70). The HbA1c levels, representing long-term blood sugar control, varied from 5.0% to 13.0%, with a mean of 7.258 (SD = 1.9604); 60% of participants had HbA1c levels below 7 (n = 120), and 40% had levels above 7 (n = 80). The central foveal thickness (CFT) as measured by OCT ranged from 211 to 651 μm , with a mean thickness of 353.55 μm (SD = 129.476). A majority of 65% (n = 130) had CFT measurements below 300 μm , while 35% (n = 70) had measurements above 300 μm . The descriptive data highlight the variability in age, duration of diabetes, glycemic control, and retinal thickness among the participants, which will be further analyzed in relation to diabetic retinopathy.

Among males, 71.4% had a CFT greater than 300 μm , compared to 61.5% with a CFT less than 300 μm , although this difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.162). Age-wise, individuals aged 51-60 years were more likely to have a CFT greater than 300 μm (42.9%) compared to other age groups, but the association was not statistically significant (p = 0.149). A longer duration of diabetes (more than 10 years) was associated with a lower likelihood of having a CFT greater than 300 μm (28.6%), compared to those with a duration of less than 10 years (71.4%), with a marginally significant p-value (p = 0.056). Notably, HbA1c levels showed a strong association with CFT; 78.6% of participants with HbA1c levels above 7 had a CFT greater than 300 μm , compared to only 21.4% of those with HbA1c levels below 7 (p

= 0.000), indicating a significant relationship between poor glycemic control and increased CFT.(Table 2)

There is a significant weak negative correlation between the duration of diabetes and HbA1c levels ($r = -0.190$), suggesting that as the duration of diabetes increases, HbA1c levels tend to decrease slightly, although this relationship is not strong, indicating that other factors may also play a role. A significant moderate negative correlation exists between the duration of diabetes and central foveal thickness (CFT) ($r = -0.264$), meaning that as the duration of diabetes increases, CFT tends to decrease, reflecting a trend toward a thinner central fovea in individuals with longer diabetes duration.(Fig 1) Conversely, there is a significant moderate positive correlation between HbA1c levels and CFT ($r = 0.446$), indicating that higher HbA1c levels, reflecting poorer glycemic control, are associated with increased retinal thickness, a common feature in diabetic retinopathy.(fig 2) The strong positive correlation between age and the duration of diabetes ($r = 0.733$) suggests that older individuals are more likely to have had diabetes for a longer period, indicating a robust linear relationship between these two variables. These findings suggest that both the duration of diabetes and glycemic control (HbA1c levels) significantly influence central foveal thickness in diabetic retinopathy, with the relationships varying in strength.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study reveal a significant association between HbA1c levels and central foveal thickness (CFT) among patients with diabetes mellitus, highlighting the critical role of glycemic control in the development of diabetic macular edema (DME). Our findings align with previous studies that demonstrate a positive correlation between higher HbA1c levels and increased retinal thickness, suggesting that poor glycemic control is a significant risk factor for macular edema in diabetic patients.(10)

The significant moderate positive correlation between HbA1c levels and CFT ($r = 0.446$) observed in our study supports the established understanding that higher HbA1c levels, indicating poorer long-term blood glucose control, are associated with increased macular thickness due to fluid accumulation and retinal swelling. This is consistent with findings from previous research, such as the Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) and the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS), which reported that intensive glycemic control reduces both the development and progression of diabetic retinopathy (DR) and its associated complications, including DME. (11)

Interestingly, our study also found a significant moderate negative correlation between the duration of diabetes and CFT ($r = -0.264$), suggesting that longer diabetes duration is associated with a thinner central fovea. This finding is supported by other studies, such as those by Yau et al. (12) and Klein et al. (7), which indicate that while longer diabetes duration is a known risk factor for DR, it may be associated with varying degrees of macular thickening depending on additional factors such as the presence of DME, the extent of microvascular damage, and glycemic control history. Moreover, the weak negative correlation between the duration of diabetes and HbA1c levels ($r = -0.190$) in our study suggests that while HbA1c levels may tend to decrease slightly over time, likely due to

stricter management protocols in long-standing diabetes, other factors like age, duration of disease, and overall health status may influence this outcome.

Notably, our findings demonstrated that 78.6% of participants with HbA1c levels above 7% had a CFT greater than 300 μm , reinforcing the significant relationship between poor glycemic control and increased retinal thickness, as reported in earlier studies.(13) This highlights the importance of maintaining HbA1c levels below 7% to minimize the risk of developing DME and subsequent visual impairment. The results are further corroborated by Parashar et al. (2016), who found that patients with HbA1c levels of 7% or above had a statistically significant increase in macular thickness measured by OCT, particularly in those with a shorter duration of diabetes (10).

Additionally, while gender and age showed no statistically significant correlation with CFT in our study, we observed a trend where individuals aged 51-60 years were more likely to have increased macular thickness. This may reflect the combined effects of aging and diabetes-related microvascular damage, as suggested by Tan et al. (2016), who noted that advanced age contributes to the severity of DR due to cumulative vascular insult over time (14).

Our study emphasizes the need for regular monitoring of macular thickness using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and stringent glycemic control to prevent or mitigate the progression of diabetic retinopathy. The use of OCT as a non-invasive imaging tool allows for the early detection and continuous monitoring of macular changes, which is critical for timely intervention (7).

In conclusion, our findings suggest that both the duration of diabetes and HbA1c levels significantly influence central foveal thickness, with poor glycemic control being a key modifiable risk factor for increased macular thickness. These results underscore the importance of intensive glycemic management in diabetic patients to reduce the risk of visual impairment associated with DME.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the significant impact of glycemic control on central foveal thickness (CFT) in patients with Diabetes Mellitus. The strong positive correlation between HbA1c levels and increased CFT highlights poor glycemic control as a major risk factor for the development of diabetic macular edema (DME). Furthermore, the findings suggest that longer duration of diabetes is associated with a decrease in CFT, likely reflecting the cumulative effects of diabetes on retinal health. The results emphasize the importance of maintaining HbA1c levels below 7% to prevent or mitigate the risk of DME and associated visual impairment. Regular monitoring of macular thickness using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and adherence to stringent glycemic control protocols are crucial strategies to reduce the burden of diabetic retinopathy and improve patient outcomes. Future studies should explore additional factors influencing CFT and investigate the role of early intervention strategies in preserving visual function in diabetic patients.

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Table 1: Association of Demographic and Clinical Factors with Central Foveal Thickness in Diabetic Retinopathy

FACTORS	DEFINITION	LESS THAN 300	MORE THAN 300	P VALUE
SEX	MALE	80(61.5%)	50(71.4%)	0.162
	FEMALE	50(38.5%)	20(28.6%)	
AGE	39-50	40(30.8%)	25(35.7%)	0.149
	51-60	45(34.6%)	30(42.9%)	
	61-70	45(34.6%)	15(21.4%)	
DM DURATION REFRAME	LESS THAN 10 YEARS	75(57.7%)	50(71.4%)	0.056
	MORE THAN 10 YEARS	55(42.3%)	20(28.6%)	
HBA1C REFRAME	LESS THAN 7	105(80.8%)	15(21.4%)	0.000
	MORE THAN 7	25(19.2%)	55(78.6%)	

Fig 1: Correlation between CFT and Diabetes Duration

Fig 2: Correlation between CFT and HbA1C